

TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR AND EMPLOYEES' CYNICISM BEHAVIOUR IN FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT:

This study examined the relationship between transactional leadership behavior and employee cynicism in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State. The sample consist of 245 randomly selected employees from six (6) purposively drawn fast-moving consumer goods companies in Port Harcourt. A quasi-experimental research design was used, and data were collected through a cross-sectional survey using a questionnaire. Contingent reward, active management by exception and passive management by exception were dimensions for transactional leadership, while affective, cognitive and behavioural cynicisms were the measures of employee cynicism. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey approach and the Pearson Product Moment correlation method was adopted in giving answers to the formulated hypotheses. The study findings revealed a positive but weak and significant relationship between contingent reward and affective, cognitive and behavioral cynicisms respectively. Similarly, active management by exception was revealed to have a positive but weak and significant relationship with affective, cognitive and behavioral cynicisms respectively. Conversely, passive management by exception was revealed to have a very strong positive and significant relationship with affective, cognitive and behavioral cynicisms respectively. Based on the findings above, the study concludes that transactional leadership behavior can be a tool in the management of employee cynicism. Specifically, the study concludes that passive management by exception can be more effective tool in controlling employees' cynicism in the workplace than contingent rewards and active management by exception. Based on the findings and conclusions above, the study recommends that Fast-moving consumer goods companies should promote workplace positivity, encourage pro-social behaviours, and draw and effective reward system as these will help build meaning and add value to the jobs done by the employees so as to decrease cynical behaviours. Organisations should encourage collaboration among employees in the workplace, emphasize effective and timely supervision, and promote mentorship programmes as these are active management practices that will inhibit the growth of employees' cynicism. Other theoretical and managerial implications for managing employees' cynicism in the workplace are also discussed.

KEYWORDS:

Active Management by Exception, Affective Cynicism, Behavioural Cynicism, Cognitive Cynicism, Contingent Reward, Employee Cynicism, Passive Management by Exception, Transactional Leadership Behaviour.

1. THE CONTEXT OF THE PROBLEM

The rate at which organisations remain in business is determined by the way and manner in which workers respond to meeting organizational goals and objective. There have been relevant studies on the relationship between the performance of employees at work and their state of mind or their perceptions towards their employing organisations (Waheed et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2016). They argued that the behavior put up by employees is a function of the perceptions they have towards the organization. On this backdrop, Özler and Atalay (2011) defined employee cynicism as the ill feelings employees have towards their organization, its management, and it is a resultant of trust.

Employee cynicism has become a recurring practice with employees' awareness of the organizational millennial goals, development and practices (Twenge, Zhang, & Im, 2004). Alhassan (2020) understudied the relationship between employees' cynicism and the level of education in tertiary institutions in Ghana. The study revealed that level of education is related to the display of cynical behaviours, with the senior staff being the ones to display the highest level of cynicism. Similarly, Panchali and Seneviratne (2019) examined the causal relationship between employees' cynicism towards their employing organisations and their performance. The study maintained that there is an inverse causal influence of cynicism on the performance of the workers.

Considering the importance of employees to all organizational activities, it becomes paramount that their feelings and perceptions for or against their organization matters a lot. This premise has left the management and employers' of labour with one question, what can inhibit the ill feelings of workers towards their employing organisations? In like manner, the leadership of organisations plays a vital role in determining the state and level in which an organization is or should be. On this backdrop, Ecler (2021), defined transactional leadership as one relationship between a leader and followers that is based on attaining organizational goals through rewards and punishment systems.

Aarons (2006) understudied the effect of leadership on the attitude of workers in relation to their mental health. The study found that leadership styles will determine the perceptions in which workers display in the organization and their responses towards introduced organizational change systems and agents. Dong (2023) carried out a comprehensive review on transactional leadership and performance of employees. The study claimed that transactional leadership enhances performance, but when not controlled inhibits innovativeness and growth. Similarly, Mekonnen and Bayissa (2023) maintained that transactional leadership is a prerequisite for organizational change. Furthermore, they noted that transactional leadership style is a contributor to the successful application of transformational leadership within an organization.

Based on the discussion above, it could be said that there exists a gap on the relationship between transactional leadership style and employee cynicism within organisations. In order to fill this gap, this study will examine how contingent rewards, active management by exception and passive management by exception can be used as methods to checkmate the ill behaviours and feelings of employees towards their employing organisations.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is presented in figure 1 below.

Source: Conceptualized by Researcher

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Showing the Hypothesised Relationship between Transactional Leadership Behaviour and Employees' cynicism

The independent variable in this study is Transactional Leadership Behaviour. The dimensions of transactional leadership behaviour were adapted from Jensen et al. (2019). On the other hand, the dependent variable in this study is employees' cynicism. The measures of employees' cynicism were adapted from the study of Durrah, Chaudhary and Gharib (2019),

Research Questions

This study intends to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between contingent rewards and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
2. How does contingent reward system relate to cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between contingent rewards and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between active management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
5. How does active management by exception relate to cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
6. What is the relationship between active management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?

7. What is the relationship between passive management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
8. How does passive management by exception relate to cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?
9. What is the relationship between passive management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State?

Based on the research questions above, the following hypotheses were formulated for this study:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₅: There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₆: There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₇: There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₈: There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Ho₉: There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

I. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR

Anita (2021) examined transformational and transactional leadership styles on the performance of workers in Ghana. The study defined transactional leadership as a leadership style with all focus on the organisations' goals attainment. She found that the leadership styles within an organization is reflected in the behavior displayed by the workers. Hussain et al. (2019) studied the relationship between transactional leadership and organizational creativity, and found that transactional leadership through the dimension of contingent reward initiates organizational creativity by enhancing the individual innovativeness of the employees.

Abdelwahed, Soomro, and Shah (2022) defined transactional leadership as management tool for attaining organizational set goals and objectives. They further noted that leadership styles are used in specific times, and that the main purpose of transactional leadership is to push performance and drive

productivity in workers. Similarly, Alrowwad, Abualoush, and Masa'deh (2020) maintained that the possession of good intellectual capital by leaders help them in determining what mix of leadership styles should be applied. They further maintained that transactional leadership through its reward system is a major determinant of performance in an organization.

Contingent Reward

Li, Jiang, He and Zhang (2022) defined contingent reward as a transactional leadership pattern that appreciates work done with reward. Furthermore, they explained that contingent reward leadership is applied for improved performance, despite the fact that their findings indicated that contingent reward has a U-shaped influence on the performance of workers. Similarly, Byron and Khazanchi (2012) defined contingent reward leadership as the leadership principle which rewards the accomplishment of routine tasks. They noted that this leadership principle drives performance in workers, and further motivates employees to the attainment of goals and organizational objectives. Gerhart (2017) asserts that contingent reward is an incentive pay given to employees with the sole aim of driving performance and motivation in workers.

Malik, Butt, and Choi (2015) found in their study that contingent reward leadership maybe use in fostering creativity and improved performance in workers. They maintained that the viability of the method depends on its applicability in relation to the leaders' capabilities and relationship with the workers. In like manner, Eisenberger and Aselage (2009) argued that contingent reward has the primary role of promoting performance, and supports team work within an organization as the workers seek means within themselves to ensure that organizational goals and objectives are met.

Active Management by Exception

Gehani, Anukool and Vivek (2019) defined active management by exception as a form of leadership style that focuses on correction and strict observance of the rules within the organization in which such leadership is practiced. Furthermore, they maintained that active management by exception brings about improvements, and provides the required support and guide needed for the execution of a project. Similarly, Bass and Avolio (2002) maintained that exceptionally active management entails support for the found digressions or errors, and inculcates practical ways to handle the organizational issues differently.

According to Yao, Woan and Ahmad (2017), active management by exception is a leadership style geared towards the unique attainment of set organizational objectives and goals. It does not encourage waste, but teaches adherence to policies and procedures of the organization. They concluded that active management does not only give support, but teaches the required applicability and practice. Similarly, Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan and Waqas (2012) defined active management by exception as the leadership that trains and guides workers in their expected responsibilities and needed organizational procedures. They further concluded that active management is the required force for driving organizational performance, as it has the capacity to assist during work challenges and prevents work problems.

Passive Management by Exception

Gehani, Anukool and Vivek (2019) defined passive management by exception as a leadership style that encourages the presence of the supervisor or manager only in the situation of error or failed process. They emphasized that passive management is a reactive method of leadership. Similarly,

Harold and Holtz (2015) maintained that passive management by exception is a leadership style that tries to avoid organizational problems, which may result into poor reinforcements of the needed workplace behaviours for organizational growth and improved workers' performances.

In the same manner, Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan and Waqas (2012) claimed that passive management leaders allow the situation to fail before intervening in the process. Furthermore, they claimed that this leadership style does not provide the required organizational management support for projects within the organization, but it is a method that continually seeks to punish failures and creates no room for tolerance.

EMPLOYEES' CYNICISM BEHAVIOUR

Feldman (2000) defined employee cynicism as an attitude or feelings of hopelessness and frustration resulting from their perceptions of distrust and dishonesty towards their employing organisations. Sunhyuk, Kiwon, Grimm, and Lee (2019) defined employee cynicism as workers ill feelings and behaviours against their employing organisations, caused by their perceptions that the organization can never be trusted and can't be honest. Ajzen (2001) defined employee cynicism as negative attitudes and feelings that employees display due to their mistrust for their organisations.

Pugh, Skarlicki, and Passell (2003) maintained that employee cynicism are behaviours put forward by workers because of their disbelief towards their employing organisations. Furthermore, they emphasized that such behaviours and feelings hinders the performance of workers in the organisations. Koçoğlu-Sazkaya (2014) defined employee cynicism as negative behavioural attitudes of employees resulting in negative work outcomes. Furthermore, he noted this attitude hinders work productivity and performance (Aslan & Eren, 2014). Ince and Turan (2011) averred that employee cynicism are negative attitudes of resentment for the organisations, and can be behavioural, cognitive or affective.

Affective Cynicism

Abraham (2000) defined affective cynicism as employees' feelings of fear, resentment, wrath, boredom, disappointment resulting from their perceptions about their employing organisations. Furthermore, he maintained that these emotions do not allow workers to function optimally. Turner and Valentine (2001) defined affective cynicism as strong emotional feelings of employees against their employing organisations. They claimed that these feelings creates undesirable perceptions in the workers, and hinders their decision-making processes. On their part, Ince and Turan, (2011: 106) defined affective cynicism as the emotional and sentimental responses to the state of awareness of the dishonesty and credibility of the actions and practices of the organization.

Cognitive Cynicism

Rehan (2017) defined cognitive cynicism as employees' skepticisms on the organisations' integrity resulting from their perceptions that the organisations lacks fairness, honesty and sincerity to keep their part of any bargain. Urbany (2005) defined cognitive cynicism as employees' skepticism about their employing organisations. The feelings of workers that organizational procedures and processes will always betray their trust is known as cognitive cynicism (Dean, Brandes, & Dharwadkar, 1998).Atawi, (2012: 20) defined cognitive cynicism as the employee's belief that principles such as justice, credibility and sincerity sacrificed to achieve the interests of the organization.

Behavioural Cynicism

The display of harsh and strong negative criticism to organizational processes and decisions to the extent of denigration and demeaning attitudes is called behavioural cynicism (Turner & Valentine, 2001). Greenberg and Baron (2008) claimed that behavioural cynicism is the display of attitudes that are noticeable against the organization. Rehan (2017) defined behavioural cynicism as employees' negative attitudes such as sarcastic humour, criticisms, negative interpretations of organizational outcomes, badmouthing. Dean et al., (1998) defined behavioral cynicism as the negative behavior of employees towards the organization, which degrades the value and importance of the organization.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

The study carried out by Mete (2013) on ethical leadership and organizational cynicism of academics in Thrace universities had the sole aim of understanding how ethical leadership predicts organizational cynicism. Four hundred respondents were sampled from three universities in Thrace. The study found that ethical leadership has an inverse influence on organisational cynicism of academics in the understudied universities. The study maintained that perceived ethical leadership from the academics, which includes fairness, integrity and openness were major determinants of organizational cynicism.

The study conducted by Demirçelik and Korkmaz (2017) with the purpose of determining the relationship between leadership styles perceived by teachers and the organizational cynics in Kayseri. The study adopted the purposeful sampling method and a total of 142 teachers were sampled. The study adopted questionnaire, and after the statistical correlation, the study revealed that school principals mostly exhibit transformative leadership behaviours. Furthermore, it found an inverse relationship between the transformational leadership dimension and the cognitive and behavioural dimensions of organizational cynicism. The study concluded that transformational leader's influence on cognitive and behavioural dimensions of organizational cynicism is direct.

The work of Chidinma, Dimgba, Micheal, Ikon and Onwuchekwa (2022) on employee cynicism and organizational performance in Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 380 obtained from a population of 4,560 employees in the Logistics firms in the South-West region of Nigeria. The study found that organizational cynicism has a positive significance on employee performance. Furthermore, bullying was found to display a direct relationship to employee turnover. The study concludes that logistics companies should reduce bullying so as to decrease the effect of cynicism in the organisations, for the effective improvement on performance.

Panchali and Seneviratne (2019) examined the relationship between organizational cynicism and employee performance in Sri Lanka, using four auditing firms. A sample of 120 was obtained. The study found that there is an inverse relationship between organizational cynicism and employee performance. It further concluded that audit firms should introduce policies that will prevent the development of cynic behaviours within the organisations.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The gathering of information from an unbiased group or population so as to ascertain a phenomenon is known as a survey (Ancker, Silver, Miller & Kaushal, 2013). The survey research design was adopted for this study, and precisely a cross-sectional design applied. Setia (2016) defined a cross-sectional research design as a research design that involves the collection and gathering of

information from different individuals or groups of persons at a single point. This study adopted the cross-sectional design. The population of this research involves all the fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State employees.

This study adopted the use of both purposive sampling and random sampling techniques. In purposive sampling technique, the researcher carefully selects the participants which he/she feels represents the required characteristics of the study objectives (Setia, 2016). Six fast-moving consumer goods companies were selected purposively. The study randomly selected the employees from each of the selected fast-moving goods companies. This selection amounted to one hundred and fifty respondents from the fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Table 1: Sample distribution of the fast-moving consumer goods companies

S/N	FMCG	Location	Respondents
1	Dufill Prima Foods (Indomie)	115 Aluu Road, off East-West Road, Choba, Port Harcourt	132
2	Multipro Consumer Product Ltd	Plot 117 Trans-Amadi Road, Trans-Amadi, Port Harcourt	84
3	Nigerian Bottling Company	Plot 126 Trans-Amadi Layout, Port Harcourt	165
4	White Diamond Salt Ltd.	Plot 97, Rivoc Road, Trans-Amadi, Port Harcourt	68
5	Crown Flour Mills	7b Azikiwe Road, Port Harcourt	98
6	New RIVOC	Plot 80/81 Rivoc Road, Trans-Amadi, Port Harcourt	85
			632

Source: Field Data, 2024

The selected workers formed a representation of the target population. The researcher adopted the Taro Yamene’s formula in determining the sample size.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Therefore, sample size

$$n = \frac{632}{1 + 632(0.05)^2} = 245$$

A total of two hundred and forty-five (245) respondents, including managers, supervisors and floor workers in the FMCG companies in Port Harcourt were sampled. The proportional allocation method, which is Bowley’s method was adopted in the distribution of the sample size within the companies sampled. The proportional allocation of population has the formula for its distribution as below:

$$\text{Distribution of sample size} = \frac{\text{Group population}}{\text{Total population}} * \text{Sample size}$$

Table 2: Table showing proportional allocation of sample size distribution

S/N	FMCG	Population	Sample Allocation
1	Dufill Prima (indomie)	132	51
2	Multipro Consumer Product Ltd	84	33
3	Nigerian Bottling Company	165	64
4	White Diamond Salt Ltd.	68	26
5	Crown Flour Mills	98	38

6	New RIVOC	85	33
		632	245

The research instrument for this study is the questionnaire. For the employee cynicism, four questions were developed for each of the variables, affective cynicism (4), cognitive cynicism (4), and behavioural cynicism (4) while the dimensions of transactional leadership have four for each of the variable, active management by exception (4), passive management by exception (4) and contingent reward (4). A total of 24 items were developed, bordering on the variables under examination, and scaled in the Likert 5-scaling system. The scaling ranged from 1-5, where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = uncertain, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree.

The method of data analysis adopted was the Pearson Product Moment statistic. This analytical tool was adopted based on its appropriateness, since the way the questionnaire was formulated to showcase ordinal kind of questions. Ordinal form of questions measured the perceptions of the respondents.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The formulated research hypotheses were examined and inferences determined in this section. The administered questionnaire, were retrieved, and the responses gathered from the respondents collated. The Pearson value, if positive indicates a direct relationship, but if negative indicates an inverse relation. A direct relationship implies a when one of the variable is increasing, the other variable will also increase, but an inverse relationship implies that while there is an increase in one variable, there is a decrease in the other variable. The Pearson values ranged between -1 or +1. The strength of each relationship depends on the value of the correlation as indicated by the Pearson correlation value. $\pm 0.00-0.19$ implies a very weak correlation, $\pm 0.20-0.39$, a weak correlation; $\pm 0.40-0.59$, a moderate correlation; $\pm 0.60-0.79$, strong correlation; and $\pm 0.80-0.99$, indicates a very strong correlation. The decision criteria for every bivariate relationship at a confidence interval of 95% or significance level of 5% is dependent on the probability value. A $p < 0.05$ implies a rejection of the null hypothesis, while a $p > 0.05$ implies an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 3: Correlation matrix for contingent reward and the measures of employee cynicism

		Contingent Reward	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioural
Contingent Reward	Pearson Correlation	1	.240**	.151*	.238**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.018	.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Affective	Pearson Correlation	.240**	1	.856**	.643**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.151*	.856**	1	.548**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018	.000		.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Behavioural	Pearson Correlation	.238**	.643**	.548**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	245	245	245	245

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The Table 3, gives the statistical representation on the relationships that exist between the variables as hypothesized.

Ho₁: *There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₂: *There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₃: *There is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

As shown in Table 3 above, contingent rewards was revealed to have a positive but weak and significant correlation with the measures of employees' cynicism in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State: affective cynicism ($r=0.240$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); cognitive cynicism ($r=0.151$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); and behavioural cynicism ($r=0.238$, $p= 0.000<0.05$). The positive correlation implies a direct relation between the variables. The probability value is 0.000, which happens to be less than 0.05, therefore, null hypotheses one, two, and three (**Ho₁**, **Ho₂** and **Ho₃**) above which states that "there is no significant relationship between contingent rewards and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism, respectively) in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State" is rejected. Since it is a two-way test, the rejection of a null hypothesis implies the acceptance of an alternate form. On this premise, the alternative hypothesis which states that "there is a positive but weak and significant relationship between contingent rewards and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism respectively) of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State" is accepted.

These findings **Ho₁**, **Ho₂** and **Ho₃** conform to the research findings by Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan and Waqas (2012), Mete (2013) and Demirçelik and Korkmaz (2017). Following the observed relationship, this study further maintains that contingent rewards is used to boost performance and helps in curtailing the ill feelings workers have against their employing organisations. It is possible that the existing direct relationship may have been triggered by the level of unemployment in the country, which may be one of the determinants for organisations not to reward workers adequately as they perceive.

Table 4: Correlation matrix for active management by exception and the measure of employee cynicism

		Active	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioural
Active	Pearson Correlation	1	.221**	.205**	.249**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Affective	Pearson Correlation	.221**	1	.856**	.643**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.205**	.856**	1	.548**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.000

	N	245	245	245	245
Behavioural	Pearson Correlation	.249**	.643**	.548**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	245	245	245	245

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Table 4, gives the statistical representation on the relationships that exist between the variables as hypothesized.

Ho₄: *There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₅: *There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₆: *There is no significant relationship between active management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

As shown in Table 4 above, active management by exception was revealed to have a positive but weak and significant correlation with the measures of employees' cynicism in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State: affective cynicism ($r=0.221$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); cognitive cynicism ($r=0.205$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); and behavioural cynicism ($r=0.249$, $p= 0.000<0.05$). The positive correlation implies a direct relation between the variables. The probability value is 0.000, which happens to be less than 0.05, therefore, null hypotheses four, five and six (**Ho₄**, **Ho₅** and **Ho₆**) above which states that "there is no significant relationship between active management by exception and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism, respectively) in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State" is rejected. Since it is a two-way test, the rejection of a null hypothesis implies the acceptance of an alternate form. On this premise, the alternative hypothesis which states that "there is a positive but weak and significant relationship between active management by exception and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism respectively) of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State" is accepted.

These findings **Ho₄**, **Ho₅** and **Ho₆** conform to the research findings by Durrah, Chaudhary and Gharib, M. (2019), Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan and Waqas (2012), Mete (2013) and Demirçelik and Korkmaz (2017). The competence of employees grants them some level of self-control and mastery over their jobs, organizational responsibilities and duties. These attributes enable the employees to develop passion and likeness for their jobs, and as such satisfaction is created.

Table 5: Correlation matrix for passive management by exception and the measure of employee cynicism

		Passive	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioural
Passive	Pearson Correlation	1	.974**	.887**	.672**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Affective	Pearson Correlation	.974**	1	.856**	.643**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000

	N	245	245	245	245
Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.887**	.856**	1	.548**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	245	245	245	245
Behavioural	Pearson Correlation	.672**	.643**	.548**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	245	245	245	245

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Table 5, gives the statistical representation on the relationships that exist between the variables as hypothesized.

Ho₇: *There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and affective cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₈: *There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and cognitive cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

Ho₉: *There is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and behavioural cynicism of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.*

As shown in Table 4 above, passive management by exception was revealed to have a very strong positive and significant correlation with the measures of employees' cynicism in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State: affective cynicism ($r=0.974$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); cognitive cynicism ($r=0.887$, $p= 0.000<0.05$); and a strong correlation with behavioural cynicism ($r=0.672$, $p= 0.000<0.05$). The positive correlation implies a direct relation between the variables. The probability value is 0.000, which happens to be less than 0.05, therefore, null hypotheses four, five and six (**Ho₇**, **Ho₈** and **Ho₉**) above which states that "there is no significant relationship between passive management by exception and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism, respectively) in fast-moving consumer goods companies in River State" is rejected. Since it is a two-way test, the rejection of a null hypothesis implies the acceptance of an alternate form. On this premise, the alternative hypothesis which states that "there is a very strong positive and significant relationship between passive management by exception and the measures of employees' cynicism (affective cynicism, cognitive cynicism, and behavioural cynicism respectively) of employees in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State" is accepted.

These findings **Ho₇**, **Ho₈** and **Ho₉** conform to the research findings by Panchali and Seneviratne (2019) and Durrah, Chaudhary, and Gharib. (2019). The passive management allows for failures before correction, which may have the propensity to instigate poor feelings from workers in terms of communication, perceptions of favoritism and the poor performance state. These issues may inhibit the attainment of projected organizational success, thereby resulting in feelings of resentment and badmouthing of the organization. These attributes and concepts may increase the widening gaps in the hearts of the employees in relation to their employing organisations, and as such, brew negative thoughts which may develop into cynicism.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The relationship between transactional leadership behaviour and employees' cynicism, as evident in fast-moving consumer good companies in Rivers State, showed a direct relationship. The summary of the findings is as follow;

- i. Contingent reward has positive but weak correlation with affective, cognitive and behavioral cynicism respectively in the understudied fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.
- ii. Active management by exception has a weak positive correlation with affective, cognitive and behavioural cynicisms respectively as evidenced in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.
- iii. Passive management by exception had a very strong positive correlation with affective, and cognitive cynicisms respectively as evidenced in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.
- iv. Passive management by exception had a strong positive correlation with behavioural cynicism as evidenced in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Based on the findings above, the study concludes that contingent rewards and active management by exception can be tools in controlling cynicism levels in fast-moving consumer goods companies in Rivers State.

Based on the findings and conclusion above, the following recommendations were made as ways of reducing employees' cynicism and getting the desired organizational outcome;

- i. Fast-moving consumer goods companies should promote workplace positivity, encourage pro-social behaviours, and draw an effective reward system as these will help build meaning as well as value to the jobs done by the employees so as to decrease cynical behaviours in the workplace.
- ii. Organisations should encourage collaboration among employees, emphasize effective and timely supervision, and promote mentorship programme as these are active management practices that will inhibit the growth of employees' cynicism in the workplace.

APPENDIX

TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR SCALE						
S/N	Items	Strongly Disagree =1	Disagree =2	Neutral/ Not Sure =3	Agree =4	Strongly Agree=1
Contingent Reward						
1	Provides me with assistance in exchange for my efforts.					
2	Discusses in specific terms that is responsible for achieving performance target.					
3	Makes clear what one can expect to receive when performance goals are achieved.					
4	Expresses satisfaction when I meet expectations.					
5	Makes innovative suggestions to improve department					
Active Management By Exception						
1	Focuses attention on irregularities, mistakes, exceptions and deviations from standards.					
2	Concentrates his/her full attention on dealing with mistakes, complains and failures.					
3	Keep track of all mistakes.					
4	Direct my attentions to failures to meet standards.					
Passive Management By Exceptions						
1	Fails to interfere until problems becomes serious.					
2	Waits for things to go wrong before taking action.					
3	Shows that he/she is a firm believer in 'if it ain't broke down don't fix it'					
4	Demonstrates that problems must become chronic before I take action.					

ORGANISATIONAL CYNICISM SCALE						
S/N	Items	Strongly Disagree =1	Disagree =2	Neutral/ Not Sure =3	Agree =4	Strongly Agree=1
1	I believe that my company (my organization) says one thing and does another.					
2	My company's (my organization's) policies, goals, and practices seem to have little in common.					
3	My company (my organization) expects one thing of its employees, but rewards another.					
4	When I think about my organization, I experience aggravation					
5	When I think about my organization I get angry					
6	When I think about my organization, I get tension					
7	When I think about my organization, I feel a sense of anxiety					
8	I complain about what is happening in the work to my friends beyond my institution.					
9	We look at each other in a meaningful way with my colloquies when my institution and its employees are mentioned.					
10	I criticize the institution's practices and policies with others.					

Source: Brandes, P, Dharwadkar, R. & Dean, J. W. (1999). *Does Organizational Cynicism Matter? Employee and Supervisor Perspectives on Work Outcomes. Eastern Academy of Management Proceedings, 150-153. Outstanding Empirical Paper Award.*

REFERENCES

- Aarons G. A. (2006). Transformational and transactional leadership: association with attitudes toward evidence-based practice. *Psychiatric Services (Washington, D.C.)*, 57(8), 1162–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ps.2006.57.8.1162>
- Abdelwahed, N. A. A., Soomro, B. A., & Shah, N. (2022). Predicting employee performance through transactional leadership and entrepreneur's passion among the employees of Pakistan. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, xxxx. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2022.03.001>
- Abraham, R. (2000). Organizational cynicism: Bases and consequences. *Genetic, social, and general psychology monographs*, 126(3), 269.
- Ajzen, I. (2001). Nature and operation of attitudes. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 27-58.
- Alhassan, I. (2020). A study of organizational cynicism among employee groups in a multi-campus public university in Ghana: Does the level of education matter? *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7(7), 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.77.8533>
- Alrowwad, A., Abualoush, S. H., & Masa'deh, R. (2020). Innovation and intellectual capital as intermediary variables among transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and organizational performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 39(2), 196–222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-02-2019-0062>
- Al-Atwi, A. A. H. (2012): "Interpretation of the phenomenon of organizational cynicism in organizations through the interconnection of the processes of psychological contract and internal respect, an analytical study of the views of a sample of workers in the Muthanna Cement Plant." *Qadisiyah Journal of Administrative and Economic Sciences*, Vol.14, No. 2: 8-8
- Anita, B. (2021). Assessing transactional and transformational leadership on workgroup behaviour. 1-6.
- Aslan, Ş., & Eren, Ş. (2014, June). The effect of cynicism and the organizational cynicism on alienation. In *The Clute Institute International Academic Conference* (pp. 617-625).
- Byron, K., & Khazanchi, S. (2012). Rewards and creative performance: a meta-analytic test of theoretically derived hypotheses. *Psychological bulletin*, 138(4), 809.
- Brandes, P, Dharwadkar, R. & Dean, J. W. (1999). Does Organizational Cynicism Matter? Employee and Supervisor Perspectives on Work Outcomes. Eastern Academy of Management Proceedings, 150-153. Outstanding Empirical Paper Award.
- Chidinma M., Dimgba, Micheal A., Ikon and Faith Chidi Onwuchekwa (2022). Organizational cynicism and employee performance of logistics companies in Southwest, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 10(1), 18-34.
- Dean Jr, J. W., Brandes, P., & Dharwadkar, R. (1998) Note Organizational cynicism. *Academy of Management review*, Vol. 23, No. 2 (April), PP. 341-352.

- Demirçelik, E., & Korkmaz, M. (2017). The relationship between the leadership styles of school managers and organizational cynicism according to the perceptions of secondary school teachers. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 7(12), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.26466/opus.309630>
- Dong, B. (2023). A systematic review of the transactional leadership literature and future outlook. *Academic Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 21-25. <https://doi.org/10.54097/ajmss.v2i3.7972>
- Durrah, O., Chaudhary, M., & Gharib, M. (2019). Organizational Cynicism and Its Impact on Organizational Pride in Industrial Organizations. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(7), 1203. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16071203>
- Ecler, J. (2021). Transactional leadership. *American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research*, 14, 399-400. 10.34297/AJBSR.2021.14.002021.
- Eisenberger, R., & Aselage, J. (2009). Incremental effects of reward on experienced performance pressure: Positive outcomes for intrinsic interest and creativity. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 30(1), 95-117.
- Feldman, D. C. (2000). The Dilbert syndrome: How employee cynicism about ineffective management is changing the nature of careers in organizations. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 43(8), 1286-1300.
- Gehani, H. K., Anukool, H. & Vivek, K. (2019). A study of management by exception: Active, passive & laissez-faire leadership style of leaders in B School.. XI. 151-161.
- Gerhart, B. (2017). Incentives and pay for performance in the workplace. In *Advances in motivation science* (Vol. 4, pp. 91-140). Elsevier.
- Greenberg, J., & Baron, R. A. (2008). *Behavior in organizations*.
- Harold, C. M. & Holtz, B. C. (2015). The effects of passive leadership on workplace incivility. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36(1), 16-38.
- Hussain, S. T., Abbas, J., Lei, S., Jamal Haider, M., Akram, T., & Nisar, T. (2017). Transactional leadership and organizational creativity: Examining the mediating role of knowledge sharing behavior. *Cogent Business & Management*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2017.1361663>
- İnce, M., & Turan, Ş. (2011). Organizational cynicism as a factor that affects the organizational change in the process of globalization and an application in Karaman's public institutions. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 37(37), 104-121.
- Jensen, U. T., Andersen, L. B., Bro, L. L., Bøllingtoft, A., Eriksen, T. L. M., Holten, A.-L., Jacobsen, C. B., Ladenburg, J., Nielsen, P. A., Salomonsen, H. H., Westergård-Nielsen, N., & Würtz, A. (2019). Conceptualizing and measuring transformational and transactional leadership. *Administration & Society*, 51(1), 3-33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399716667157>

- Koçoğlu-Sazkaya, M. E. R. V. E. (2014). Cynicism as a mediator of relations between job stress and work alienation a study from a developing country Turkey. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*, 6.
- Li, C., Jiang, X., He, H., & Zhang, X. (2022). The influence of performance-contingent rewards on proactive and responsive creativity: Dual-path mediating effects of work motivation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 812298. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.812298>
- Malik, M. A. R., Butt, A. N., & Choi, J. N. (2015). Rewards and employee creative performance: Moderating effects of creative self-efficacy, reward importance, and locus of control. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36(1), 59-74.
- Mekonnen, M., & Bayissa, Z. (2023). The effect of transformational and transactional leadership styles on organizational readiness for change among health professionals. *SAGE open nursing*, 9, 23779608231185923. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23779608231185923>
- Mete, Y. A. (2013). Relationship between organizational cynicism and ethical leadership behaviour: A study at higher education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 89, 476-483. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.08.880.
- Nemr, M. A. A., liu, Y., & Wright, L. T. (2021). The impact of ethical leadership on organizational citizenship behaviors: Moderating role of organizational cynicism. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1865860>
- Özler, D. E., & Atalay, C. G. (2011). A research to determine the relationship between organizational cynicism and burnout levels of employees in health sector. *Business and management review*, 1(4), 26-38.
- Panchali, J., & Seneviratne, S. M. (2019). Organizational cynicism and employee performance: Evidence from a Sri Lankan Audit Sector. *Annals of Management and Organization Research*, 1(2), 155-169.
- Panchali, J., & Seneviratne, S. M. (2019). Organizational cynicism and employee performance: evidence from a Sri Lankan audit sector. *Annals of Management and Organization Research*, 1(2), 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.35912/amor.v1i2.409>
- Paracha, M. U., Qamar, A., Mirza, A., Hassan, I. & Waqas, H. (2012). Impact of leadership style (transformational & transactional leadership) on employee performance & mediating role of job satisfaction: Study of private school (educator) in Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(4), 55-64.
- Pugh, S. D., Skarlicki, D. P., & Passell, B. S. (2003). After the fall: Layoff victims' trust and cynicism in re-employment. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 76(2), 201-212.
- Rehan, M. (2017). Organizational cynicism and its relationship with employee's performance in teaching hospitals of Pakistan.
- Sharma, N. P., Sharma, T., & Agarwal, M. N. (2016). Measuring employee perception of performance management system effectiveness: Conceptualization and scale development. *Employee Relations*, 38(2), 224–247. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-01-2015-0006>

- Stanley, D. J., Meyer, J. P., & Topolnytsky, L. (2005). Employee Cynicism and Resistance to Organizational Change. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 19(4), 429–459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-005-4518-2>
- Sunhyuk, K., Kiwon, J., Grimm, N. & Lee, K. (2019). What makes employees cynical in public organizations? Antecedents of organizational cynicism. *Social Behavior and Personality: an International Journal*, 47, 1-10. 10.2224/sbp.8011.
- Turner, J. H., & Valentine, S. R. (2001). Cynicism as a fundamental dimension of moral decision-making: A scale development. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 34, 123-136.
- Twenge, J. M., Zhang, L., & Im, C. (2004). It's beyond my control: A cross-temporal meta-analysis of increasing externality in locus of control, 1960-2002. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 8(3), 308–319. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr0803_5
- Urbany, J. E. (2005). Inspiration and cynicism in values statements. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 62, 169-182.
- Waheed, A., Abbas, Q., & Malik, O. F. (2018). Perceptions of performance appraisal quality and employee innovative behavior: Do psychological empowerment and perceptions of HRM system strength matter? *Behavioral sciences (Basel, Switzerland)*, 8(12), 114. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs8120114>
- Yao, L., Woan, K.S. & Ahmad, M.H.B. (2017). The relationship between leadership styles and employee engagement: Evidences from construction companies in Malaysia. *Medwell Journal, The Social Sciences*, 12(6), 984-988.